

Effects of Bibliotherapy and Mentoring Counselling Techniques on Career Indecision among Post-Basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of Bibliotherapy and Mentoring Counselling Techniques on career indecision among Post-Basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State. The objective of the study was to assess the effects of both techniques on the cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions of career indecision. Six null hypotheses were raised and tested at a 0.05 significance level. The study adopted quasi-experimental design specifically pretest and posttest design. The population of the study consists of 275 Post-Basic Education Students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Gusau Educational Zone identified with higher career indecision. out of them 60 students were sampled to participate in the study. Two data collection instruments were used for the purpose of the study: Validated Career Decision Scale (CDS) with reliability index of 0.903 was used for identification, while validated Career Decision Making Difficulties (CDDQ) with reliability index of 0.804, 0.864, 0.915 and 0.904 for the three dimensions of career indecision and the overall questionnaire was used for pretest and posttest. Statistical analysis, specifically t-tests for related sample was used to test the hypotheses of the study at 0.05 level of significant. The study revealed that, both Bibliotherapy and Mentoring Counselling Techniques were significantly effective in reducing career indecision across all three dimensions. It was concluded that both Bibliotherapy and Mentoring counseling techniques were significantly effective in the treatment of cognitive, affective and behavioral dimensions of career indecision. The study recommends that schools and career counsellors incorporate both Bibliotherapy and Mentoring Counselling Techniques into career guidance efforts.

Keyword: Bibliotherapy, Mentoring, Career Indecision, Post-Basic Education Students

Introduction

The issue of career indecision is one of the significant issues within the field of career and vocational guidance that has attracted the interest and attention of researchers. It is a common problem among individuals, especially students, and can impede career decision-making and choice processes. Career indecision is the inability of an individual to select or choose an occupation, or the challenges and difficulties that emerge in arriving at the occupational decision. This phenomenon appears to be a common experience among students who are contemplating their future working life. This difficulty in career decision-making leads to three major consequences, as highlighted by Chen and Liew (2015): individuals may transfer decision-making to others, leading to failure in optimal career choices and, in certain cases, temporary unemployment. These complications lead to a state of "career indecision," a focal point for researchers, as indicated by Xu, (2020).

The major symptoms of career indecision often include a lack of accurate information about occupational choices, combined with unrealistic self-perceptions, low motivation, and societal or familial pressures. Additionally, individuals may struggle with identity diffusion, finding it challenging to define clear career goals and lacking a distinct sense of self. Trait indecision may be prevalent, where individuals face general decision-making difficulties extending to their career choices. Choice anxiety arises, leading to stress and apprehension when confronted with numerous career options. Moreover, disagreements with others may exert pressure to pursue specific career paths that contradict an individual's personal interests or values (Kulcsár, et al., 2020).

Various types of career indecision encompass distinct experiences that individuals may encounter. These include the "Uninformed," where individuals lack information about career options and have not explored diverse paths; the "Conflicted," who struggle with decision-making due to conflicting values, interests, or goals; the "Procrastinators," who delay and may even avoid contemplating their careers; the "Hyper-vigilant," who obsess over making the "right" choice to the point of decision paralysis; and the "Inconsistent," who frequently change their minds and have difficulty committing to a specific career path (Levin, et al., 2022). Others are "Developmental Indecision," considered a developmentally typical issue where individuals may lack career information, struggle with defining career goals and a clear identity, and find general decision-making challenging, "Chronic Indecisiveness" which represents a prolonged pattern of difficulty in decision-making, often characterized by persistent delays, an excessive fear of making mistakes, frequent changes in decisions, and an inability to commit to a career path, "Hyper-vigilant Indecision" which involves individuals who hastily choose a career goal based on inadequate self-knowledge or understanding of the work environment, often responding prematurely due to stress or other factors (Guay, et al., 2006). Conversely, "Vigilant Indecision," as outlined by Boye, (2020), pertains to individuals who also select a career goal but with more informed knowledge of themselves and their environment, leading to a decision made with lower stress and anxiety levels, resulting in the most positive attitudes towards their career choices. These distinct types highlight the various aspects of career indecision experienced by individuals.

Career indecision encompasses a complex interplay of cognitive, affective, and behavioral factors/dimensions. From a cognitive perspective, career indecision is often characterized by a lack of accurate information about career, unrealistic self-perceptions, and difficulties in defining clear career goals. Individuals may struggle with identity diffusion, finding it challenging to develop a distinct sense of self and their vocational interests. The affective dimension involves choice anxiety, leading to stress and apprehension when confronted with numerous career options. Negative emotions such as fear, doubt, and low motivation can hinder the career decision-making process. Behaviorally, career indecision may manifest as procrastination, avoidance of career-related tasks, and difficulties in initiating or committing to a career decision. Disagreements with significant others, such as family members and peer influence can also exert pressure on individuals to pursue specific career that contradict their personal interests or values, thereby complicating the behavioral aspects of career indecision (Kulcsár, et al., 2020 & Gati, et al., 2012).

To address the challenges of career indecision effectively among post-Basic Education Student in Gusau Educational Zone, two counseling techniques were employed: Bibliotherapy and Mentoring Counseling Techniques.

Bibliotherapy is a counselling approach that involves using literature, including books, poetry, and other written materials, as a means of helping individuals explore and understand their emotions, thoughts, and experiences. It is otherwise known as biblioguidance, bibliocounselling, literatherapy, book-matching or reading therapy. Bibliotherapy is used to address emotional and behavioral problems and meet therapeutic goals. It can be used in both educational and mental health settings, and it involves selecting reading materials that match the client's interests and reading skills. Bibliotherapy can help people understand the issues they are experiencing, normalize experiences with mental health concerns and care, and offer hope for positive change. It is believed to be a cost-effective and versatile option for the treatment of several mental health issues, including depression, anxiety, and substance dependency (Good Therapy, 2016 & Verywell Mind, 2021).

In the context of career indecision, bibliotherapy can help students and individuals increase their career motivation and confidence by providing guidance and support through literature. It can provide valuable insights and assistance for individuals contending with career indecision. Bibliotherapy is a resourceful method in the context of career decision-making. It can guide individuals through the complexities of selecting a career path, fostering empathy and self-awareness by connecting them with narratives that mirror various career journeys. Moreover, bibliotherapy aids in processing the anxieties associated with career decisions by offering a cathartic release through engagement with literature. It also plays a role in facilitating a transformative shift in perspective, encouraging understanding of diverse career options and their potential impact. The qualitative results of a study on bibliotherapy with the career topic showed that students experienced positive changes in expression, gesture, and self-confidence after participating in the program (Eliasa & Iswanti, 2014).

On the other hand, mentoring counselling technique has evolved from the integration of mentoring and counselling principles, providing a comprehensive approach to supporting individuals in their personal and professional development. Mentoring involves the provision of guidance, advice, and support by a trusted individual, while counselling focuses on exploring and resolving personal and emotional challenges. The combination of these two practices in mentoring counselling signifies recognition of the holistic nature of career decision-making, addressing not only the rational and logical aspects but also the emotional and personal dimensions of an individual's journey (IvyPanda, 2024 & Training Course Material, 2021).

One of the key postulations behind mentoring counselling technique is the acknowledgment that career decisions are deeply intertwined with an individual's values, emotions, and personal identity. Career indecision often arises from internal and external factors, including self-doubt, societal expectations, and lack of clarity about personal goals. Mentoring counselling posits that a supportive and guidance-focused relationship can empower individuals to navigate through these challenges (Heinrichs et al., 2021 & American Psychological Association.2012).

Mentoring Counselling places a significant emphasis on creating a safe and open space for mentees to explore their career indecision. Through active listening, empathetic communication, mentors guide mentees in understanding the root causes of their indecision and help them identify their strengths, values, and interests, aligning them with potential career paths. The role of a mentor in this context is not only to provide answers but to facilitate a mentee's self-discovery, enabling them to make informed and authentic career choices that resonate with their personal and professional aspirations.

The responsibility of making career decisions largely falls on the individual, which can pose challenges if the person lacks essential decision-making skills. Ukil (2016) points out that in underdeveloped and developing societies, youths often struggle with decision-making because cultural norms typically restrict adolescents from independently making career decisions. This pattern is observable in Nigerian culture where a majority of parents take charge of determining their children's career paths. Although, the responsibility of decision-making rests on the individual, challenges often arise when the person lacks necessary occupational information to base his/her decisions upon. Nathan and Hill (2006) suggest that an inability to make a career decision may stem from various other underlying causes. Jamali, et al., (2015) highlighted over 50 factors associated with career decision-making challenges, categorizing them into inner factors such as: stress, self-esteem, decision-making styles, shortage of motivation and social phobia. And outer factors such as: discrimination, shortage of sources and inter-personal. In an ideal situation, Post-basic Education Students would possess a clear understanding of their career, have access to accurate and consistent information about different career options, and exhibit the self-confidence and motivation to take decision towards their career. However, experience reveals that many Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State experience career indecision, which encompasses cognitive, affective, and behavioural dimensions.

In Zamfara State, Post-basic Education Students 1 are traditionally exposed to subject selection towards the end of the first term or at the beginning of the second term. During this process, students are asked to choose between the science, commercial, or arts streams. However, many students struggle to make this decision effectively. This pointed to the prevalence of career indecision among Post-Basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone. The inability to select an appropriate academic track often reflects the broader challenges these students face in defining their career and making informed career decision. These lead to a situation whereby most students in post basic schools in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State depend solely on their parents, guardians, teachers, friends and significant others when it comes to career decision. These resulted in many problems such as Career-related decision-making difficulties, psychological impact, and Lack of information and external limits among others. If these problems associated with career indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State are not address, it could lead to several negative outcomes. Students may struggle to make informed career choices, leading to potential mismatches between their skills, interests, and chosen career. Moreover, unresolved career indecision among Post-basic Education Students may contribute to heightened stress, anxiety, and self-doubt, impacting their overall well-being and mental health. Furthermore, the inability to take action towards their career goals may hinder students' professional development and limit their opportunities for personal and financial growth.

The outcomes of this study will be of significant importance for various stakeholders, including students, teachers, career counsellors, parents, educational policymakers, and researchers. The study covered only ten weeks and ten sessions of forty-five minute using a structured treatments program of Bibliotherapy and Mentoring Counselling Techniques on student's identified with the symptoms of the three dimensions of career indecision in Gusau, Zamfara State.

The study therefore, delimited all other counselling techniques such as solution-focused brief counselling technique, cognitive restructuring counselling technique, reinforcement counselling technique, self-management counselling technique among others. All other issues related to career such as career development, career aspiration, career decision making self-efficacy were delimited from this study. The study also delimited all private post basic schools in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State, and all post basic students II and III. All the other thirteen local governments in Zamfara State were also delimited from this study.

Objectives of the study:

The objectives of this study were to determine:

1. The effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on each of the Cognitive, affective and behavioural dimensions of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

- The effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on each of the Cognitive, affective and behavioural dimensions of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State

Hypotheses:

The following Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant in the study:

- Ho1:** There is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Cognitive dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.
- Ho2:** There is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Affective dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.
- Ho3:** There is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Behavioural dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.
- Ho4:** There is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on Cognitive dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.
- Ho5:** There is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on Affective dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.
- Ho6:** There is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on Behavioural dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Methodology

The study adopted Quasi-Experimental design in form of Pretest-Posttest design to examine the effects of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique (BCT) and Mentoring Counselling Technique (MCT) on career indecision among post-basic education students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State. The population consists of 275 Post-Basic Education Students identified with high levels of career indecision using the adapted Career Decision Scale (CDS). The adapted Career Decision-Making Difficulties Questionnaire (CDDQ) was used for pretest and posttest to measure cognitive, affective, and behavioral dimensions of Career Indecision. Both instruments were validated and found reliable through pilot testing, with correlation coefficients of 0.903 for adapted CDS and 0.804 (cognitive dimension) 0.864 (affective dimension) 0.915 (behavioural dimension) 0.915 for overall adapted CDDQ. Data collection involved administering the adapted CDS to identify students with career indecision, followed by administering adapted CDDQ during pretest, 10 weeks of BCT and MCT intervention, and administering adapted CDDQ during posttest phases. The data analyses employed was t-test for related sample to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant.

Results

The six null hypotheses formulated to guide the study were tested below in tabular form at 0.05 level of significant:

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Cognitive dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Table 1: t-test Analysis for Pre-Test and Post-Test Cognitive Dimension of Career Indecision Mean Scores Exposed to Bibliotherapy:

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Pre-test Bib. Cog.	44.63	5.055	Effective
2	Post-test Bib. Cog.	33.60	2.513	

Source: Field Data, 2025

The results in Table 1 indicates a significant reduction in the mean scores of cognitive dimensions related to career indecision after bibliotherapy intervention, with the pre-test mean score of 44.63 (SD = 5.055) decreasing to a post-test mean score of 33.60 (SD = 2.513). The lower post-test mean suggest that bibliotherapy was effective in improving participants' cognitive dimension in reducing career indecision, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis 1 which states that there is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Cognitive dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Affective dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Table 2: t-test Analysis for Pre-Test and Post-Test Affective Dimension of Career Indecision Mean Scores Exposed to Bibliotherapy:

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Pre-test Bib. Affect.	36.67	4.787	Effective
2	Post-test Bib. Affect.	26.90	3.177	

Source: Field Data, 2025

The results in Table 2 indicates a significant reduction in the mean scores of affective dimensions related to career indecision after bibliotherapy intervention, with the pre-test mean score of 36.67 (SD = 4.787) decreasing to a post-test mean score of 26.90 (SD = 3.177). The lower post-test mean suggest that bibliotherapy was effective in improving participants' affective dimension in reducing career indecision, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis 2 which states that there is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Affective dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Behavioural dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Table 3: t-test Analysis for Pre-Test and Post-Test Behavioural Dimension of Career Indecision Mean Scores Exposed to Bibliotherapy:

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Pre-test Bib. Behav.	36.83	5.207	Effective
2	Post-test Bib. Behav.	26.63	2.942	

Source: Field Data, 2025

The results in Table 3 indicates a significant reduction in the mean scores of behavioural dimensions related to career indecision after bibliotherapy intervention, with the pre-test mean score of 36.83 (SD = 5.207) decreasing to a post-test mean score of 26.63 (SD = 2.942). The lower post-test mean suggest that bibliotherapy was effective in improving participants' behavioural dimension in reducing career indecision, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis 3 which states that there is no significant effect of Bibliotherapy Counselling Technique on Behavioural dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on Cognitive dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Table 4: t-test Analysis for Pre-Test and Post-Test Cognitive Dimension of Career Indecision Mean Scores Exposed to Mentoring:

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Pre-test. Men. Cog.	45.00	5.446	Effective
2	Post-test Men. Cog.	32.57	4.313	

Source: Field Data, 2025

The results in Table 4 indicates a significant reduction in the mean scores of cognitive dimensions related to career indecision after mentoring intervention, with the pre-test mean score of 45.00 (SD = 5.446) decreasing to a post-test mean score of 32.57 (SD = 4.313). The lower post-test mean suggest that mentoring was effective in improving participants' cognitive dimension in reducing career indecision, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis 4 which states that there is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on Cognitive dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Hypothesis 5

There is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on Affective dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Table 5: t-test Analysis for Pre-Test and Post-Test Affective Dimension of Career Indecision Mean Scores Exposed to Mentoring:

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Pre-test. Men. Affect.	40.38	3.995	Effective
2	Post-test Men. Affect.	28.45	4.085	

Source: Field Data, 2025

The results in Table 5 indicates a significant reduction in the mean scores of affective dimensions related to career indecision after mentoring intervention, with the pre-test mean score of 40.33 (SD = 3.995) decreasing to a post-test mean score of 28.43 (SD = 4.085). The lower post-test mean suggest that mentoring was effective in improving participants' affective dimension in reducing career indecision, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis 5 which states that there is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on Affective dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Hypothesis 6

There is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on Behavioural dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Table 6: t-test Analysis for Pre-Test and Post-Test Behavioural Dimension of Career Indecision Mean Scores Exposed to Mentoring:

S/N	Variable Name	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	Pre-test. Men. Behav.	38.57	4.150	Effective
2	Post-test Men. Behav.	28.57	4.108	

Source: Field Data, 2025

The results in Table 6 indicates a significant reduction in the mean scores of behavioural dimensions related to career indecision after mentoring intervention, with the pre-test mean score of 38.57 (SD = 4.150) decreasing to a post-test mean score of 28.57 (SD = 4.108). The lower post-test mean suggest that mentoring was effective in improving participants' behavioural dimension in reducing career indecision, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis 6 which states that there is no significant effect of Mentoring Counselling Technique on behavioural dimension of Career Indecision among Post-basic Education Students in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of this study revealed that Bibliotherapy counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of cognitive dimension of career indecision. The mean score decreased from 44.63 (SD = 5.055) to 33.60 (SD = 2.513), reflecting a substantial reduction of 11.03 (SD = 3.83). This effect was statistically significant ($t = 15.787$, $df = 29$, $p = 0.000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The significant reduction in the cognitive dimension of career indecision after bibliotherapy aligns with Taylor (2007), who found that career guidance counselling significantly reduced cognitive barriers (lack of information) among adolescents by improving knowledge about career options and decision-making processes. Similarly, Dogan and Bacanlı (2012) conducted a study to evaluate the effect of a career decision-making group guidance program on high school students' decision-making difficulties. They revealed that all levels of career decision-making difficulties including cognitive dimensions significantly decreased in the experimental group compared to the control group, indicating the program's effects.

The second finding revealed that bibliotherapy counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of affective dimension of career indecision. The mean score decreased from 36.67 (SD = 4.787) to 26.90 (SD = 3.177), showing a notable reduction of 9.77 (SD = 2.90). This effect was statistically significant ($t = 18.466$, $df = 29$, $p = 0.000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The significant reduction in the affective dimension (e.g., anxiety, emotional readiness) after bibliotherapy is consistent with study conducted by Lewis et al. (2015) on the use of bibliotherapy to treat nighttime fears in young children. They found that this approach is effective in reducing fear of the dark. They suggested that bibliotherapy could be a valuable intervention for addressing nighttime fears in young children there by indicating its relevance to affective dimension of career indecision.

The third finding of this study revealed that bibliotherapy counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of behavioural dimension of career indecision. The mean score decreased from 36.83 (SD = 5.207) to 26.63 (SD =

2.942), demonstrating a significant reduction of 10.20 (SD = 3.41). This effect was statistically significant ($t = 16.394$, $df = 29$, $p = 0.000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The significant reduction in the behavioral dimension after bibliotherapy aligns with Montgomery and Maunders (2015) who found that bibliotherapy can act on the same mechanisms as Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) and can be effective in the prevention and treatment of internalizing and externalizing behaviors, as well as strengthening pro-social behaviors. Montgomery and Maunders (2015) suggest that bibliotherapy can be an effective intervention for addressing behavioral issues in children, which may translate to improved behavioral outcomes related to career decision-making in adulthood. This finding is contrary to the findings of Dogan and Bacanlı (2012) who found that while improvements were maintained over an 11-week period following treatment, the reduction in external conflicts (behavioural dimension) did not persist.

The fourth finding of this study revealed that mentoring counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of cognitive dimension of career indecision. The mean score decreased from 45.00 (SD = 5.446) to 32.57 (SD = 4.313), reflecting a substantial reduction of 12.43 (SD = 4.27). This effect was statistically significant ($t = 15.939$, $df = 29$, $p = 0.000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The significant reduction in the cognitive dimension after mentoring aligns with Bayram and Öztirak (2023), who found that mentoring positively impacted career awareness and professional expectations. Similarly, this finding also resonates with Okurame and Ajayi (2017) who found that mentoring improved cognitive task performance, supporting the cognitive benefits observed in this study.

The fifth finding of this study revealed that mentoring counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of affective dimension of career indecision. The mean score decreased from 40.38 (SD = 3.995) to 28.45 (SD = 4.085), showing a notable reduction of 11.93 (SD = 3.33). This effect was statistically significant ($t = 19.314$, $df = 29$, $p = 0.000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The significant reduction in the affective dimension after mentoring is consistent with Milot-Lapointe et al. (2020), who found that career counselling reduced psychological distress and improved emotional readiness supporting the effect on affective dimension as observed in this finding. This finding also aligns with Lam and Santos (2018), who reported increased career decision self-efficacy and reduced career indecision after a mentoring intervention.

The last finding of this study revealed that mentoring counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of behavioural dimension of career indecision. The mean score decreased from 38.57 (SD = 4.150) to 28.57 (SD = 4.108), demonstrating a significant reduction of 10.00 (SD = 3.66). This effect was statistically significant ($t = 14.974$, $df = 29$, $p = 0.000$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The significant reduction in the behavioral dimension after mentoring aligns with Sola (2018), who highlighted mentoring's role in shaping career trajectories and improving decision-making behaviors. The finding also resonates with Babarinde et al. (2022) who found that mentoring has a positive impact on the career development of respondents, with 70% confirming its positive impact on their career. The study also found that mentoring effects has a significant effect on the career development of the respondents, with a chi-square value of 9.459 and a p-value of 0.009 at a 0.05 level of significance, further supporting the behavioral improvements observed in this study.

Conclusion

Base on the outcomes of this study, it is concluded that Bibliotherapy counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of cognitive, affective and behavioural dimensions of career indecision. Mentoring counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of cognitive, affective and behavioural dimensions of career indecision.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since the finding of this study discovered that bibliotherapy counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of the cognitive, affective and behavioural dimensions of career indecision, schools and career counselors should incorporate bibliotherapy into career guidance programs to help students overcome cognitive, affective and behavioural problems associated with career indecision.
2. Since the finding of this study discovered that mentoring counseling technique is significantly effective in the treatment of the cognitive, affective and behavioural dimensions of career indecision, schools should establish mentoring programs to help students overcome cognitive, affective and behavioural problems associated with career indecision.

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